

INTRODUCTION

Umẹwaẹn Volume Nine has three articles: one on Benin pottery and two on Benin's relations with her neighbours. The first article "Narrative of Traditional Pot Making in Modern Benin Kingdom, Southern Nigeria: A Case Study of Two Potters in Okabere and Uselu Communities" by Kennedy Eweka and Jean Borgatti employ ethnographic fieldwork, practice-led research, and visual documentation to analyze clay sourcing, preparation, production, baking, surface finishing, and distribution of clay pots as an aspect of ancestral heritage and family continuity in two Benin communities of Okabere and Uselu that have continued traditional pottery in spite of modernity and increased urbanization. Praise Osaretin's "The Nature and Dynamics of Benin-Igala relations, 1507-1897" analyzes the relations between the Benin Kingdom and the Igala kingdom, and the impact of the two wars they fought on the Igala monarchy and the cultural influences/exchanges that followed in both kingdoms. The third article, "Benin and the Urhobo Three Worlds" by Henry O. Unuajohwofia uses cultural studies and some oral literature of the Urhobo and other published sources to establish that the Urhobos have lived through three epochs (or Worlds) of which two revolve around the Benin empire, which was not completely shaken off by British colonialism and independence in Nigeria.

The volume also includes the obituaries of three scholars in Benin studies: the folklorist Prof. Dan Ben-Amos (1934-2023) and the linguist duo Pa. Gabriel O. Obaze (1934-2004) and Prof. Victor Omozuwa (1952-2024).

We are grateful to the Department of History, SUNY Oswego, for the continuous support and thank Prof. Jean Borgatti for her permission to use her photograph work for the cover page. We thank our art (Osazeomwanogie Usuanlele) and technology team (Omoruyi Usuanlele and Dr. Osariuyimen Usuanlele) who helped put this issue together.